

PERFECT LESSON PLANNING BASED ON TESOL AND TEFL PROGRAMS

Oylola Ibrohimova

Andijan State Foreign Language Institute teacher

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7165196>

Abstract. *This article deals with making perfect lesson plans based on some scholars' theories on lesson planning and especially TESOL and TEFL international teaching programs. Furthermore, it demonstrates sample perfect lesson plan including complete parts with thorough justification.*

Keywords: *TESOL (teaching English as a second language), TEFL (teaching English as a foreign language), lesson plan, warming-up, presentation, practice, application, assessment, follow-up, exit ticket, visuals.*

ИДЕАЛЬНОЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЕ УРОКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ПРОГРАММ TESOL И TEFL

Аннотация. *В этой статье рассматривается составление идеальных планов уроков на основе теорий некоторых ученых о планировании уроков и особенно международных учебных программ TESOL и TEFL. Кроме того, он демонстрирует образец идеального плана урока, включая полные части с подробным обоснованием.*

Ключевые слова: *TESOL (преподавание английского как второго языка), TEFL (преподавание английского как иностранного), план урока, разминка, презентация, практика, применение, оценка, продолжение, выходной билет, визуальные эффекты.*

INTRODUCTION

In our rapidly advancing world changes in education has a great impact on the field of teaching at the same time. All leads to teachers have to work hard to keep-in-touch up-to-date demands. Nowadays, common scale for teachers is estimated by their lesson planning skills and this causes deep research on making perfect lesson plans.

As Anthony Haynes claimed teaching is a three-step activity: the first step consists of planning and preparation – required before teaching a class; the second one is classroom management, teaching, learning; and the third of activities that take place after the lesson - assessment, with associated activities such as recording and reporting, evaluation.[1] In this article I try to illustrate the first step of teaching process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

According to majority of scientists views, planning and preparation decides the future of upcoming lesson whether it may be successful or not. One of the methodology experts D. B. Agzamova provides the clear definition of lesson planning. “Planning is often viewed as a key aspect of teaching a successful lesson. During the planning phase, the teacher makes decisions about goals, activities, resources, timing, grouping and other features.”[2]

One of the most controversial issues on organizing lesson is timing. Majority of teachers face difficulties in timing nearly every day. Lesson planning can be the only solution here, because it includes sections. Methodologists G. T. Makhkamova, Sh. S. Alimov and A. I. Ziyayev divides the lesson instructional time, engaged time and academic learning time. “When classroom procedures are completed a teacher usually gives learners instructions, it’s called instructional time. The time given to do task is called engaged time. During academic learning time learners participate actively and are successful in learning activities”.[3]

Methologist J. Jalolov claims that the most important for teachers is to define aims and objectives of a lesson. “At the beginning of the lesson planning a teacher should answer the following questions: 1) What language and speech material will students learn within this lesson? 2) What do they know and are able or unable to do before the beginning of the lesson and what results they are able to achieve?”[4]

RESULTS

Learning many scholars’ findings on lesson planning and studying TESOL and TEFL course, I learned basic materials devoted to perfect lesson planning. Having learned them, I guessed some lacks in my previous lesson planning strategy. My mistake deals with the sequence of six steps of the lesson such as warming-up, presentation, practice, application, assessment and follow-up. I got habited to organize practice after presentation, not caring whether it is controlled practice or independent practice. Now I decided to organize controlled practice first and then upcoming application part at the second stage.

Comparing my previous lesson plans to recent ones, I used to give my basic attention to give more information not thinking about students’ complete understanding and using this new data communicatively. By this way, my previous lesson plans included a couple of different activities to acquire knowledge rather than use it practically. In my performed lesson plan I sequenced warming-up, presentation, practice, application, assessment and follow-up parts of the typical lesson. In warming-up part I organized the activity “Great wind blows...” about familiar films, cartoons and shows to introduce new topic and create interest. In presentation stage perform interesting sample pictures of TV programs together with calling names to caption all pupils.

DISCUSSION

I selected controlled practice including group work activity after presentation instead of free practice. Because the flow of using practice is controlled practice, then moderately controlled practice and the last one is free practice. By this activity, students have opportunity to acquire basic information about TV programs. They practiced “Rolling turn” activity and group discussion. In application stage I used “Making up a story” continuing partner’s saying using the structure “After he had..., he ...” activity to create atmosphere for free practice. I think students have fun with concrete standardized lesson plan.

Another improvement is related to assessment stage, I used exit ticket. Students continue the clause “After I had watched TV...” and leave the room. By this way, we can identify how they learned the theme, new vocabulary and grammar.

Sample lesson plan.

Grade 8 – Unit 3. Information age. Lesson 2. After I’d watched TV...

<p><u>Materials</u></p> <p>Textbook p. 23</p> <p>Handouts.</p> <p>Pictures</p> <p>Cards to practice topic vocabulary</p>	<p><u>Agenda</u></p> <p>Check HW: “Stand up/sit down</p> <p>Warm-up: “Great wind blows...”</p> <p>Introduce new vocabulary by pictures</p> <p>Practice new vocabulary: “Rolling turn”</p> <p>Listening practice</p> <p>Introducing grammar</p> <p>Practice grammar: Storytelling</p>
---	---

<u>SLOs</u>	
Encounter new vocabulary (TV programs) in context	
Practice listening for specific word	
Use past simple and past perfect tense for past actions	
Time	Procedures
5	Check HW from previous lesson; “Stand up/sit down” activity for checking learnings in Unit 2, give objectives; put the theme on board
5	Warming-up. “Great wind blows...” about familiar films, cartoons and shows to introduce new topic and create interest.
7	Main part. Introducing new vocabulary Open textbook p. 23, look at exercise 1 Perform interesting sample pictures of TV programs together with calling names to caption all pupils Do choral practice of starter topic words in the box (teach correct pronunciation)
10	
10	Practice new vocabulary. Divide groups of 4 randomly (by numbers) Introduce the language which new words are used What channels/programmes do you like watching? Do you know any soap operas? What is your favourite cartoon? Instruct how to do “Rolling turn” activity and model Monitor group discussions
10	
10	Listening Ask pupils to read the questions in exercise 2 and underline key points Play the tape. Students listen and try to find answers Ask students to check each other’s work with elbow partners. Play the tape for the 2 nd time Announce answers to the group that one can correct wrong responses.
10	
10	Grammar Create interest by giving question “What did you do yesterday?” Introducing new grammar by notes on the floor activating students by going ahead and back. Hand out cards with sample questions using past simple and past perfect. Ask students to think over possible answers for them. e.g. A: (What did you after you had got up?) B: After I had got up I made breakfast Students select cards asks and answer questions.
10	
10	Story telling

	Instruct how to organize “story telling”, model. Students make up a story continue partner’s saying using the structure “After he had..., he ...
3	Assessment Exit ticket: Students continue the clause (name of the theme “After I had watched TV...”) and leave the room
Remaining	Summarize the theme Announce the homework: writing “My last Sunday”

CONCLUSIONS

Hence, lesson planning is hard work taking step-by-step procedure into consideration selecting proper activities for six parts. Besides, students’ desire and age also plays a vital role. Well-planned lesson provides great classroom management and helps to create enjoyable and effective lesson.

REFERENCES

1. Anthony Haynes. The complete guide to lesson planning and preparation. – Continuum international publishing publishing group, 2010, - p.1.
2. D. B. Agzamova. English teaching methodology. – T: Barkamol fayz mediya, 2016, - p.12.
3. G.T.Makhkamova, SH.S.Alimov, A.I.Ziyayev. Innovative pedagogical technologies in the English language teaching. – T: Fan va texnologiya, 2017, - p.178-179.
4. J.J.Jalolov, G.T.Makhkamova, SH.S.Ashurov. English language teaching methodology – T: Fan va texnologiya, 2015. – p. 252.
5. Svetlana Xan, L. Kamalova, L. Jo’rayev. Teens’ English – T: O’qituvchi, 2020, - p.23.